

Word Reading Processing by Bilingual Speakers: Brazilian Portuguese and English with and without ADHD

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Abstract. The research explores the relationship between bilingualism and ADHD, based on the way bilingual people process word reading. Faced with the many benefits of bilingualism for the individual, we set out to investigate what would happen if we combined the two phenomena. It is a fact that the bilingual person has improved executive control. Therefore, would it be beneficial for the subjects with ADHD if they were bilingual? The hypothesis for our study is that bilingual participants with ADHD would perform equivalently to bilingual participants without ADHD. We carried out a self-monitored reading task of isolated words, to measure the reading time of the words and the index of correct answers. The material consists of a set of 48 word/non-word/pseudoword pairs. The dependent variables are reading time for the first word, reading time for the second word, response time for the lexical decision of the word/pseudoword/non-word and index of correct answers. The independent variables are frequency and length of words and group of bilinguals (with and without ADHD). The results indicated that the bilingual participants with ADHD read the first and second word in less time than the group without ADHD and had an equivalent correct index, presenting evidence that points to an improved executive control for the bilingual subjects.

Keywords: Language Processing; Bilingualism; ADHD; Executive control

1 Introduction

One of the central interests of Experimental Psycholinguistics is to understand how people process verbal language, and what are the mental processes involved in this processing in real time (Leitão, 2005). Within this, there are several specific interests, ranging from investigations at the phonological level to the semantic-pragmatic levels, both in the native language and in the second language (L2). Among the objects of study of Experimental Psycholinguistics, there is an interest in studying how the linguistic processing of words occurs.

In contrast to bilingualism, Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is associated with poor executive control (Barkley, 2020; DiGirolamo et al., 2001; Sonuga-Barke et al., 2010) and its main symptoms are: inattention, impulsivity, and hyperactivity (American Psychiatric Association, 2014). Onset of these symptoms typically occurs before age 12 years and has been present for at least six months, and in at least two settings. Children with ADHD have other difficulties in language development and academic functioning, such as, for example, an impoverished linguistic functioning, such as difficulty in retelling stories, producing long sentences, interaction skills in each context (Bellani et al., 2011).

ADHD is considered a public health problem, due to impairments in the cognitive, social, family, academic, and occupational spheres of people with this disorder, generating costs to society (Diller et al., 1996; Nevin, 2003). One of these impairments is in working memory, which can influence the speed of word recognition, due to the size of the sequence of letters or sounds (Beyersmann et al., 2011). The linguistic processing of reading demands the identification of words through the recognition of letter sounds and/or direct lexical access, converting graphic signs into phonological representations. The grapheme/phoneme conversion is initially carried out slowly, during literacy, characterized by a syllabic reading rhythm that occurs by the phonological route (Cavalheiro et al., 2010). The reading process starts with visual processing, followed by letter

decoding, a task that requires attention and concentration. For subjects with ADHD, this path may fail, as they have difficulty maintaining concentration, also impairing textual comprehension, making it necessary to repeat the reading.

In view of the studies showing the benefits of bilingualism for the individual, and the differences in processing for this group, we propose to investigate what happens if we combine the two phenomena. Would the possibility of an improved executive control for bilinguals then be beneficial for the subject with ADHD since they have a deficit in executive control? Can bilingualism act upon favouring the processing of reading isolated words compared to monolingual individuals with ADHD?

The main objective of this research was to investigate the reading time of words in bilingual L1-Brazilian-Portuguese and L2-English speakers with and without ADHD. The specific objectives aim to analyse the linguistic factors that influence the lexical processing (lexical decision - word vs. non-word and high vs. low frequency of a word) in bilinguals, to correlate the improvement of executive control in bilinguals with the attentional factor in ADHD in a self-monitored reading task with lexical decision, and to investigate whether the lexical linguistic frequency influences the reading time and the task among the tested groups. To do so, we conducted a psycholinguistic experiment comparing the performance of linguistic processing between bilinguals with and without ADHD.

This research is within the scope of Experimental Psycholinguistics regarding the linguistic processing of bilingual subjects with and without ADHD. Through observation through the experimental task of self-monitored reading of words with lexical decision, we will investigate the reading times of the words and the response.

2 Lexical Access

A variety of models have been proposed to explain how the bilingual mental lexicon is organised. Schwartz & Kroll (2006) observed that there is a hierarchical structure of words and concepts. The Word Association model says that ‘L2 words access meaning indirectly through the L1’ (op. cit.), i.e., the L2 words are represented in the bilingual’s mind as the equivalent L1 translation. The Concept Mediation model proposes that ‘L2 words have direct access to their respective meanings’ (op. cit.).

The revised hierarchical model (RHM), proposed by Kroll & Stewart (1994), integrates the two previous models and is able to take into account changes in connections between words and concepts as L2 acquisition progresses. RHM assumes, at the lexical level, that ‘the L2 to L1 connection is stronger than the L1 to L2 connection’ (Schwartz & Kroll, 2006, p. 971) due to the stage at which learners use L1 translations to retrieve the meaning of L2 words. Therefore, L1 connections to concepts are stronger than L2 connections, but the model recognizes that, as language proficiency increases, L2 connections to concepts start to become like L1 connections. As a concept mediation model, RHM accounts for the possibility of skilled bilinguals accessing concepts directly through L2 words. Evidence for RHM comes from translation experiments and semantic categorization tasks (Dufour & Kroll, 1995). It is the first model to explain changes in mental representation during second language acquisition.

Dijkstra & Van Heuven (2002), present a connectionist model called BIA+, (Model of Bilingual Plus Interactive Activation) which aims to explain and simulate, through computational modelling, how the asymmetric patterns observed in bilingual processing occur. In this model, the lexicons of the bilingual’s languages are incorporated into a single component, thus as he argues that there is no separation between languages during processing, that is, non-selective lexical access. As its name suggests, BIA+ is an expanded version of an existing model, the BIA (Van Heuven et al., 1998) which, in turn, is based on the monolingual Interactive Activation model of McClelland and Rumelhart (1981),

whose distinction between them lie in the simplification of the model, as well as the inclusion of elements not previously considered by the BIA. Basically, the model did not take into account external factors not linguistic elements, such as context, types of tasks and other aspects, as well as phonological and semantic elements. Due to the various limitations presented by the model, especially in relation to the description and functionalities of the linguistic nodes responsible for identifying the language corresponding to a given stimulus, and the lack of morphological and semantic representations, the need to modify it arose. Unfortunately, BIA and BIA+ only simulate spelling recognition of 4-letter (or 5-letter) words; the lexical-semantic representations are not implemented.

The most recent model is the Multilink (Dijkstra et al., 2019), a computational model for bilingual word recognition and word translation. This model considers the findings obtained with the BIA/BIA+ and RHM models and integrates them into the Multilink model. One of Multilink's objectives is to go beyond the spelling recognition of 4-letter (or 5-letter) words simulated by BIA and BIA+, simulating now the recognition of 3- to 8-letter words, including cognates of different lengths. While the BIA/BIA+ models consider word retrieval during language comprehension, RHM addresses language production issues, in particular word translation (Dijkstra & Rekké, 2010, pp. 403–407). According to the RHM, in the early stages of L2 acquisition, the meaning of words presented in the L1 is retrieved directly but retrieving that of the L2 words requires mediation through the L1 translation equivalent. This indirect mediation proceeds through word association links between representations of L2 and L1 word forms.

A word in one language is presented to a bilingual in a printed or spoken form who then produces its translation into another language, usually in spoken form. This 'translation production' task covers both reverse translation (L2 to L1) and direct translation (L1 to L2). In this task, participants must actively generate a response based on their knowledge of the foreign language (De Groot et al., 2000). On the other hand, in the translation recognition task, participants decide as quickly as possible whether the target is a correct prime translation or not. The Multilink model distinction is in activating their semantic representations in a way associated with the orthographic representations activated in the input (Dijkstra et al., 2019) and the semantic representations activate the non-selectively linked phonological representations of the language. As multiple lexico-phonological representations of the input and output language are co-activated, there must be a task-dependent decision process that ensures that the correct translation in the correct language is produced.

A computational model like Multilink helps us understand the mechanisms underlying the retrieval of bilingual words both qualitatively and quantitatively. Multilink sheds light on how various underlying mechanisms interact and function. For example, particular assumptions on the input or output side can be added or omitted to see if they are essential to generate specific Reaction Time patterns (e.g., asymmetry of translation effects). Thus, a computational model such as Multilink inspires the modeler to generate new hypotheses for empirical testing, as it allows simulations of complex interactions between many variables (Dijkstra et al., 2019).

Brybaert & Duyck (2010, p. 364) presented evidence of 'L1 and L2 words acting very much as if they were words of the same language, interacting with each other as part of the word identification process', indicating little evidence for separate lexicons. In Interactive Activation (IA) models, languages can only be seen as separate to the extent that there is a difference in the size of lateral inhibition (between orthographic or lexical phonological nodes) within and between languages. In Multilink, it is assumed that there are no inhibitory side effects between words, nor between languages, as a kind of null hypothesis.

In Multilink model, in which connections between L2 words and their meanings are stronger, word forms are characterized by a frequency-dependent resting (waiting) level activation. As bilinguals with different L2 proficiency use L2 words more or less frequently, this implies differences in resting level activation for L2 words. Multilink was developed with the aim of providing an implemented

general description of word form and meaning retrieval during word recognition and production (Dijkstra & Rekké, 2010). Future developments of the model aim to explore, for example, whether the intensity of relationships between meaning and resulting sonority may depend on language proficiency.

Psycholinguistic models of the bilingual mental lexicon focus on which level of representation – orthographic/phonological, lexical or conceptual level – bilingual languages are interconnected (Isel et al., 2010). Understanding this phenomenon guides the investigations conducted with multilingual individuals, delimiting the starting and ending point of interference of the second language on the first, as well as assessing the real extent of this relationship.

3 Bilingualism

The phenomenon of bilingualism is the subject of much debate and discussion, not only regarding its definition, but also its relevance. As for its definition, it pervades the questions of how to know that the individual is bilingual, and how to determine their level of proficiency. Schwartz & Kroll (2006) define as bilingual individuals who actively use two languages with some degree of proficiency and explain that they rarely tend to be ‘equally proficient or balanced in the use of two languages, making one of the languages the most dominant in the language’ (p. 968). Researchers such as Grosjean (2012) define bilinguals as ‘those who use two or more languages (or dialects) in their everyday lives’ (p. 4). Furthermore, bilinguals do not form a homogeneous group, they vary in age and form of acquisition, level of proficiency and how much they use their languages.

Bilinguals can be dominant in one of their languages or balanced, but defining the notion of language mastery is difficult. The criteria for this definition are based on fluency, use, reading and writing skills, with fluency as a highlight. In the literature, it is possible to find subjective fluency, when participants self-report their fluency in languages in a background questionnaire; and objective fluency, when the researchers assess the fluency of the participants through assessment instruments, which are proficiency tests or evaluative tests carried out by the researchers themselves. Furthermore, bilinguals may not develop full and equal fluency in all language skills (speaking, listening, reading and writing) and their linguistic repertoire may change over time depending on the degree of use of one or more knowledge languages. Experimental research has suggested that both languages of a bilingual are activated jointly, even when the context does not require activation of both (Grosjean, 2012).

In this fertile field for investigative research on the possible benefits of bilingualism, studies such as Mårtensson et al. (2012) suggested that ‘the learning of foreign languages in adults is accompanied by increases in the volume of grey matter in brain regions related to language’ (p.244). Mechelli et al. (2004) found ‘an increase in grey matter density in the left inferior parietal cortex of bilinguals relative to monolinguals that is more pronounced in early bilinguals than in late bilinguals’ (p.757).

3.1 Bilingualism and Interfaces

3.1.1 Bilingualism and Executive Control

Executive functions are cognitive processes that control behaviour in the service of goal achievement (Diamond, 2013). These cognitive skills are essential for planning behaviour, ignoring irrelevant information, attending to stimuli and information of interest, and creativity. Executive function skills change throughout life because of cognitive maturation and after age-related decline (Dempster, 1992). They are also malleable and respond to short- and long-term experiences (Diamond & Lee, 2011), which leads us to infer that bilingualism affects executive functioning in some way, given that constant

monitoring, inhibition, selection, and planning are essential components of everyday bilingual language use. What can be expected is that bilingual language processing will rely more on general domain executive functions than in the case of monolinguals, and transfer effects will give bilingual advantages in executive functions, according to results from tests such as Stroop, Simon, and Flanker Task.

An experiment performed by Bialystok et al. (2017) with bilingual children with ADHD presented evidence for a more laborious linguistic processing in bilingualism, which means a reduced vocabulary in each language and slower word retrieval. However, aspects of cognitive processing, in particular executive control, have been improved. ADHD was associated with a weakened executive control system, with symptoms of inattention, impulsivity and hyperactivity. Language, Flanker, and Stop signal proficiency tests were taken and an interesting result has been presented regarding language proficiency; the one-way ANOVAs comparing the two bilingual groups showed that bilinguals with ADHD, rated themselves more proficient than non-ADHD bilinguals in English proficiency. There was no self-reported evidence of language proficiency disadvantages for bilingual individuals with ADHD, indicating that in the college student sample, ADHD may be associated with high verbal functioning.

A few years later, Chung-Fat-Yim et al. (2019) present a study pointing to the impact of bilingualism on executive control, now with bilingual adolescents performing better on tasks than monolinguals. As we saw in Section 2.1, research has shown that even when only one language is needed, bilinguals activate the lexicons of both languages in parallel (Kroll et al., 2012). Due to this joint activation, the bilingual brain must manage language selection by focusing its attention on the language in question, and in return, ignore the interference of the other language, which presumably occurs through the recruitment of general attention mechanisms (Bialystok, 2015). The unique experience of bilinguals in managing attention to two conjointly activated languages is training in selective attention, a crucial element of executive function. Bilingual adolescents showed higher levels of executive functioning than their monolingual peers on the standard flanker task, a result also found with children. Bilingualism has been linked to improved attention skills.

3.1.2 Bilingualism and Brain Plasticity

Throughout this research, we have presented evidence that bilingualism acts on neural networks, and it is widely accepted that this phenomenon changes the brain (Pliatsikas et al., 2014b). These changes in brain structure are indicators of experience-dependent plasticity and impact brain function and thus executive functions. Bilingualism affects brain regions that serve cognitive control, including the left inferior frontal gyrus, anterior cingulate cortex, inferior parietal lobe, and basal ganglia, particularly the putamen and left caudate nucleus (Abutalebi & Green, 2016). Bilinguals have greater grey matter density than monolinguals in several brain structures, including the left inferior parietal lobe, which is modulated by age of acquisition and proficiency (Mechelli et al., 2004), as well as the caudate nucleus (Zou et al., 2012) and the cerebellum (Pliatsikas et al., 2014b). Bilinguals also have greater white matter integrity than monolinguals (Luk et al., 2011).

Rose et al. (2013) studied 15 bilingual children for one year and found that inferior parietal lobe grey matter density increased and was related to language ability and cognitive control. Gold et al. (2013) observed that older adult bilinguals had lower blood oxygen level-dependent response (indicative of processing with less effort) than monolinguals in several frontal regions and exhibited superior task-switching skills. Zou et al. (2012) found that grey matter volume of the anterior cingulate cortex (an area implicated in executive control) in bilinguals was positively correlated with functional activity and negatively correlated with a behavioural conflict effect. A few years later, Abutalebi et al. (2015) in a study on the neuroprotective effects of bilingualism with older Chinese adults, reported increased grey matter in the anterior cingulate cortex, while monolinguals showed decreased grey matter in the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (which plays a crucial role in executive functions), and these

brain differences correlated with the advantage of bilinguals over monolinguals on the Flanker task. These findings suggest that bilinguals benefit from more efficient executive function processes and that this can be observed in the anatomical correlates of the processes in question.

Cognitively stimulating activities, both long term and short term, lead to cognitive benefits, brain changes and improved cognitive outcomes of aging. Bilingualism is one such cognitive stimulus, and possibly involves a significantly larger brain network than, say, crosswords or Sudoku puzzles or learning to play an instrument (Antoniou, 2019). This evidence supports the view that bilinguals have an advantage in offsetting age-related decline.

4 Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD)

According to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5, 2014), ADHD is:

‘...a neurodevelopmental disorder defined by impairing levels of inattention, disorganization, and/or hyperactivity-impulsivity. Inattention and disorganization involve an inability to stay on task, an appearance of not listening, and loss of materials at levels inconsistent with age or developmental level. Hyperactivity-impulsivity implies excessive activity, restlessness, inability to remain seated, intrusiveness in activities of others, and inability to wait - symptoms that are excessive for age or developmental level. In childhood, ADHD often overlaps with disorders commonly considered "externalizing," such as oppositional defiant disorder and conduct disorder. ADHD often persists into adulthood, resulting in impaired social, academic, and professional functioning.’

ADHD is the most common neurodevelopmental disorder of childhood (Fontana et al., 2007). Some studies reveal that ADHD is a neuropsychiatric condition that affects 3-5% of children and that often persists into adulthood, considered one of the most common neuropsychiatric disorders. The electronic magazine ‘Consciência no dia a dia’ (2009), explains that attention deficit happens because neurotransmitters such as dopamine (main component of our cerebral reward system, a system activated every time we do something that gives pleasure and signals the brain that the experience is worth repeating) do not work as well in individuals with ADHD.

For Olivier (2010), its diagnosis can also be defined as a multifactorial disorder associated with environmental and genetic factors. Variations in brain size and morphology, where they are present very early, with abnormalities in the frontal/cerebellum circuit, mainly in the right hemisphere, thought to be responsible for most disorders of motor coordination and a subnormal sensorimotor program, in addition to other possible causes, but not widely publicised.

Inattention is a difficulty in paying attention to details or making careless mistakes in certain activities such as: difficulty maintaining attention in tasks and recreational activities, seeming not to listen when spoken to, not following instructions and not finishing tasks, difficulty organising tasks and activities, avoid engaging in tasks that require constant mental effort, losing things necessary for tasks or activities, and being easily distracted by stimuli unrelated to the task and showing forgetfulness in daily activities (DSM-5, 2014, p. 59) .

Hyperactivity refers to excessive motor activity - frequent fidgeting of hands and feet, fidgeting a lot in a chair, abandoning the chair in situations in which it is expected to remain seated, talking too much, difficulty engaging silently in activities, running in inappropriate places, giving hasty answers before questions have been completed, have difficulty waiting their turn, and frequently interrupting or meddling in other people's business (DSM-5, 2014, p.60).

Impulsivity refers to hasty actions that occur at the moment without premeditation and with a high potential for harm to the person, some common situations: crossing a street without looking, may manifest with social intrusiveness, making important decisions without consideration of long-term consequences, lapses in dispersion may generate difficulty in temporal organisation, interpersonal relationships, leading the person to generate too much effort to carry out everyday tasks and resulting in less durability and performance, difficulty playing sports, excessive forgetfulness of everyday activities such as turning off the gas, among others, difficulty maintaining a job, social group, or relationship for a long period of time, verbal impulsiveness and/or behaviours of trying to defend any action, showing aggressive behaviour, uncontrolled eating, drug use, excessive spending, varied compulsions such as for games, uncontrollable chatter, among others; they will be able to participate in several projects at the same time, affirming the need to live intensely (DSM-5, 2014, p.60).

In view of the symptoms observed for at least six months, individuals with ADHD can be classified into three subtypes: mixed or combined, predominantly hyperactive and predominantly inattentive (Fontana et al., 2007). The diagnosis of ADHD is fundamentally clinical, based on well-defined operational criteria, derived from classification systems such as the DSM-4 or the ICD-10. The DSM-4 proposes the need for at least six symptoms of inattention and/or six symptoms of hyperactivity/impulsivity for the diagnosis of ADHD. The DSM-4 and ICD-10 include a criterion of age of onset of symptoms prejudicing (before seven years old) for the diagnosis of the disorder.

4.1 ADHD and Executive Functions

The concept of executive function begins with the neuropsychological study of patients with deficiencies in this area, as well as the formulation of working memory. Baddeley (1996) organized the working memory model as a tripartite storage system consisting of a central executive and two slave systems: a phonological loop, related to the representation and recitation of verbal material, and a visuospatial buffer system, the imagery equivalent of memory. The central executive is the main component of the theory, and its functions are reasoning, decision-making, strategy planning and behaviour control through the integration of information from subordinate systems. Its operation involves learning and applying contingent rules, abstract reasoning, and maintaining attention and concentration, and its functioning is closely related to the prefrontal areas.

Van Lambalgen et al. (2008) present causal relationships between the etiology of ADHD and executive function, showing deficiencies in planning. The sample consisted of a group of 26 children with ADHD and 34 individuals without ADHD, divided according to the age group of seven to nine years. All children with ADHD categorized as 'combined type', i.e. with attention and hyperactivity problems. An important factor is the presence of comorbidity in 22 of 26 children with ADHD. For testing executive functions, the study was based on the task performed by Shue et al. (1992) who showed that children with ADHD score significantly worse than neurotypical individuals in a set of tasks involving synthesis and execution of a plan to reach a certain goal. The paradigmatic case is the 'Go/No-Go' task, whose basic structure is as follows: in one type of stimulus the subject has to press a key (this is the 'go' stimulus), in another type of stimulus the subject must not do anything (the 'no go' stimulus). Stimuli are presented in random order. In Shue et al. (1992), the 'go' stimulus is a paper showing an apple, and the 'no go' stimulus is a paper showing an ice cream; The goal is 'do (x) now', with x a variable to be instantiated. There are two rules, which can be formalised as 'if it's an apple, go (go)' and 'if it's an ice cream, go (don't go)'. This means that there are two possible unifications for the variable x in each goal, the go, and don't go actions, which reduce the goal to satisfying one of the preconditions, apple, or ice cream. The (only) successful unification then determines the action to be taken. Performance on this task in children with ADHD is significantly impaired, as many attempts to 'no go'

lead to a 'go' response, and this suggests that the initial calculation (unification and reduction of the goal 'do (x) now') is not executed correctly. If the 'go' answer is conceived as an unconditional answer, that is, if the goal is simplified to 'do (go)', it does not require any calculation. Thus, we see the performance of children with ADHD on these tasks as evidence of the difficulty of keeping a complex goal active in working memory and the tendency to simplify that goal as a result.

In the production of utterances, skills such as semantics and pragmatics in subjects with ADHD are affected. In a 'story telling' task, whose objective is to investigate which linguistic devices children use to narrate the story, subjects with ADHD present deviant narration patterns due to executive difficulties. These difficulties are corroborated by the study by Purvis & Tannock (1997) that showed in the investigation of this phenomenon with the reading of a popular tale 'The father, his son and their donkey' in which children would have to repeat the story, that there was a tendency to retell the events of the story out of sequence.

ADHD, within what was researched, is a neurological disorder and it is estimated that the causes are associated with the non-functioning of neurotransmitters such as dopamine, genetic factors, and the history of childhood. Difficulty in concentration and attention, restlessness in places like the classroom, lectures, etc., too talkative, impatient and distracted, are some of the characteristics of this group. The consequence of these symptoms is perceived in the daily life of these subjects and a lot of intervention needs to be done, both pharmacologically and through therapies.

5 Experimental Design

Although ADHD is one of the most frequent disorders in childhood and consequently one of the most studied in the child population, there are still few studies that aim to relate the cognitive function of working memory with the areas of learning difficulty in attention deficit disorder/hyperactivity in both children and adults, which are sometimes diagnosed late.

We conducted a self-monitored reading to observe how words are processed in English by bilingual subjects (Portuguese – English) with and without ADHD, at intermediate and advanced levels of proficiency. According to Mitchell (2004), the self-monitored reading technique is one of the techniques, along with eye tracking and the method that makes use of event-related evoked potentials (ERPs) through electroencephalograms (EEGs), that are timeless. In the self-paced reading technique, a subject is presented with text segmented into words, strings of words or phrases that are displayed one at a time on a computer screen. The individual himself is responsible for pressing a key so that the text or word begins to be shown, and after reading it press the key again to show the second part of the text or word and so on until the end of the task. The experiment was performed using the PennController for Internet-Based Experiments software ('PennController' or 'PCIBex' for short) which provides the tools to build and run experiments online, from familiar paradigms such as self-paced reading to completely customized paradigms.

The hypotheses we assume are that: Bilinguals with ADHD will perform similarly to bilinguals without ADHD in the self-monitored reading task with lexical decision (word versus non-word) modulated by lexical frequency - high versus low). We justify these hypotheses based on recent studies regarding the improvement on executive control of bilingual people and the better performance of ADHD bilingual people in their Language and Flanker test (Bialystok et al., 2017; Chung-Fat-Yim et al., 2019). Bilinguals will have a cognitive advantage and better performance compared to monolingual controls without ADHD.

14 volunteer subjects¹ participated in this experiment, Brazilian English speakers, seven subjects with ADHD, and seven without ADHD (control group). Within the group with ADHD, we have four subjects at the advanced level and three subjects at the intermediate level, as well as in the group without ADHD. The age between 25 and 40 years old, among the forwards we have three residents from João Pessoa, two from São Paulo, two from England, and one from Portugal. In the group of intermediaries, we have two from São Paulo, three from João Pessoa, and one from Canada. Of these participants, six are women and eight are men. There was the intention to control the medicated/non-medicated factor of each volunteer with ADHD, and so we conducted a questionnaire on Google Forms so that they could answer these questions: 1. At what stage was it diagnosed? (childhood, adolescence, adult), 2. Do you use medication? If yes, how long ago? 3. What strategies do you consciously use to deal with the disorder?

We also recorded any behavioural changes observed by them on the day the experiment was carried out, such as anxiety, fatigue, excessive lack of concentration, etc., due to external circumstances, and we instructed them to carry out the experimental task at another time, to be able to explain any time and correct answers given by participants with ADHD. Only one participant communicated that they were not feeling very well that day, possibly having an anxiety attack, and carried out the experiment two days later.

When collecting the responses from the form, we found that of the seven participants with ADHD, six were diagnosed in adulthood and had been using medication for about two to five years. Among the main responses to which strategies they use to deal with the disorder were: use of reminders, support network, physical exercise, routine, avoiding exposure to excessive stimuli, regulated sleep, controlled caffeine intake, meditation, task management, psychotherapy, paying close attention to everything you are doing, and coping cards.

5.1 Procedures

Initially, participants were informed that the research was within the scope of Experimental Psycholinguistics, and that they could withdraw from participating at any time, without prejudice. They were also informed about how many steps would be performed by them, and the approximate total time of these procedures, which was 20 to 25 minutes. In order to evaluate their proficiency level, participants answered the proficiency test, the Vocabulary Levels Test (Nation, 1990), through the *ClassMarker* platform.

The experimental task is based on experiment three of the thesis of Albuquerque (2008). The online experiment was carried out using the isolated word self-monitored reading technique, which, in this case, consisted of carefully reading two words comparing their reading times and the rate of correct answers between the groups in question. Independent variables are word frequency and length, and a bilingual group (with or without ADHD). The dependent variables are, therefore, the reading times of the words, the lexical decision time for the second word/pseudoword/non-word and the index of correct answers. The hypothesis for this experiment is that the group with ADHD will present reading times equivalent to those of the group without ADHD.

The material consisted of a set of 192 words separated by conditions: 48 high-frequency small word/pseudoword/nonword pairs, 48 high-frequency big word/pseudoword/nonword pairs, 48 pairs of low-frequency small words/ pseudowords /nonwords, and 48 low-frequency big word/pseudoword/nonword pairs. The words were taken from the Academic Word List (AWL). Since the separation of syllables in the English language has its specifications, we chose to control the size of

¹ Another 16 participants will still be tested to complete the sample of 30 participants.

the words by the number of letters, so words with four to six letters would be considered 'small' and those with seven to nine letters, 'big'.

5.2 Results

The dependent variables of the experiment were the time to read the first word (RT1), the time to read the second word (RT2), the time to answer the question at the end of the task (RT3). If the words were the same, the participants would press the F key and if they were not the same, they would press the J key. This procedure was reversed for the participants in the second round of the experiment, if the words were the same, they would press the J key and if they were not, the letter F. The last dependent variable was the hit rate.

We selected 14 participants for the first round of the experiment, separated by group and proficiency. This sample contained three participants from the control group and three participants from the intermediate-level ADHD group; and four participants in the control group and four participants in the advanced ADHD group. First, we carried out the descriptive statistics in the Jamovi software of all the reading times RT1, RT2, and RT3 and the index of correct answers in relation to all independent variables. We remove outliers using three standard deviations up and down.

Then, we performed an analysis of variance test (ANOVA) in relation to the experiment items and the variable reading time of the first word. For the dependent variable RT1, the analysis showed a main effect between groups, with and without ADHD with $F(1,298) = 116.095$ and $p < .001$ and for the length of words with $F(1,298) = 6.984$ and $p = 0.008$. There was no effect on proficiency ($p = 0.402$) or word frequency ($p = 0.485$). There was interaction factor between group * proficiency * size with values $F(1,298) = 6.974$ and $p = 0.008$ and group interaction * proficiency with $F(1,298) = 10.327$ and $p = 0.001$.

Post Hoc Tests of t -values show us exactly where the interactions identified by the ANOVA between group * proficiency occurred. The values show that the advanced ADHD group compared to the advanced control presented a shorter reading time with 329 milliseconds of average difference, with $t = 5.72$ and $p < 0.001$. The intermediate ADHD group compared to the advanced control showed a mean difference of 505 milliseconds in favour of the ADHD group with $t = 8.18$ and $p < 0.001$. The intermediate control and advanced ADHD group differed by 432 milliseconds with $t = 7.06$ and $p < 0.001$. The intermediate control and intermediate ADHD group was where we found the greatest statistical difference with $t = 9.32$, $p < 0.001$ and mean difference of 608 milliseconds. We did not find statistically significant differences between the groups, ADHD and control and their levels of proficiency, that is, advanced control group and intermediate control and advanced ADHD and intermediate ADHD group. The results showed shorter reading times in the RT1 variable for the bilingual subjects with ADHD compared to the control group, which we expected according to our hypothesis, equivalent reading times between the tested groups.

Then descriptive statistics, ANOVA and t -test for the reading time of the second word, RT2, were performed. For the dependent variable RT2, the analysis showed a main effect between the control and ADHD groups with $F(1,277) = 33.7006$, mean difference of 142, $t = 5.53$ and $p < .001$ and for the proficiency level $F(1,277) = 42.6220$, mean difference of 174, $t = 6.81$ and $p < .001$. There was interaction effect between group * proficiency with $F(1,277) = 18.5447$ and $p < 0.001$, group * proficiency * size with values of $F(1,277) = 5.5631$ and $p = 0.018$, group * proficiency * frequency with value of $F(1,277) = 4.3170$ and $p = 0.038$, group * size * frequency with $F(1,277) = 12.1782$ and $p < 0.001$ and finally group * proficiency * size * frequency with $F(1,277) = 5.1854$ and $p = 0.023$.

We observed a greater effect between groups and proficiencies regarding large words for the intermediate level, the control-intermediate- nounbig condition and the ADHD-intermediate- nounbig group with a mean difference of 290.46, $t=5.499$ and $p<0.001$, a greater distancing of the average reading time between these groups. The same for small words, the control-intermediate- nounsmall condition and the ADHD-intermediate- nounsmall group presented a mean difference of 219.35, $t=4.174$ and $p<0.001$. The condition control and advanced ADHD nounsmall showed no statistically significant difference, as well as control and advanced ADHD nounbig.

For the third dependent variable, RT3, response time to the question asked after reading the words *prime* and *target* was also analysed, and we obtained the following results. We performed an analysis of variance test (ANOVA) for the dependent variable RT3, the analysis showed a main effect between groups, ADHD and control, and the level of proficiency. With values for the group effect of $F(1,328) = 40,295$ and $p < .001$, and for the level of proficiency we have values of $F(1,328) = 147,534$ and $p < .001$. ANOVA showed interaction between group * proficiency with values and $F(1,328) = 62,558$ and $p < .001$.

The last dependent variable analysed was the rate of correct answers in relation to the group, proficiency, size and frequency, with the following results. For the index of correct answers between the groups, we found a statistically significant difference only between the proficiency levels, advanced and intermediate, with values $F(1,328) = 2.9745$ and $p = 0.085$ and interaction between group * frequency * size with values of $F(1,328) = 5.3005$ and $p = 0.021$. We observed that the intermediate-level ADHD group showed better performance in reading large words in relation to the advanced and the control group, both advanced and intermediate. This data is important for us to infer that, as we have a more favourable reading average for the ADHD group, their hit rates balanced with that of the control group, it can demonstrate that they were performing the task with attention, using their personal strategies.

5.3 Discussion

We proposed with our experiment to point out possible favours of bilingualism in the linguistic processing of typical subjects with ADHD, under the same experimental line. Aware of the impairment of ADHD with the executive function interface presented in the theoretical foundation of this research, we tested bilingual subjects, speaking Brazilian Portuguese-English, with and without ADHD and found in our sample of 14 participants, seven bilinguals with ADHD and seven bilinguals without ADHD, that participants with ADHD performed better on the experimental task. Showing shorter reading times than the control group and a balanced index of correct answers with participants without ADHD. We have lower reading time values towards the intermediate level, which we believe may be related to our sample size so far, of only 14 participants. Given the linguistic impairment that people with ADHD show in several studies, due to lack of attention, agitation, difficulty completing a task, etc., the findings found in this research seem to diverge from our initial hypothesis, that bilingual participants with ADHD would present equivalent performance with bilinguals without ADHD, but we are still moving forward with the collection of data from the other participants.

The results seem to indicate bilingualism as a compensatory tool, as we saw in the study by Bialystok et al. (2017) with bilingual children with ADHD who, despite the reduced vocabulary and weakened executive control due to the disorder, the linguistic proficiency in English of these participants was higher than bilinguals without ADHD. Evidence supported by Chung-Fat-Yim et al. (2019) pointed out the impact of bilingualism on executive control, now with bilingual adolescents, who performed tasks better than monolinguals. Bilingual adolescents showed higher levels of executive

functioning than their monolingual peers on the standard flanker task, a result also found with children. Bilingualism has been linked to improved attention skills.

Another possible explanation that we based on why participants with ADHD performed the experimental task in less time than participants without ADHD is found in Messina et al. (2009), who performed five subtests with participants with ADHD and in the Visual Working Memory subtest, observed that the ADHD group performed better than the group without ADHD and that it may be due to the effort to remain attentive during the execution of the task, making use of from other areas that arise to help them in the attentional process. In view of the responses, we obtained from the participants regarding the strategies they use daily to better deal with the symptoms of the disorder.

An interesting fact regarding the rate of correct answers of our participants is that the answers were equivalent between both groups, the same result found in Albuquerque (2008), where the subjects with ADHD did not differ from the subjects without ADHD regarding the score of the answers; they just needed more time to perform the task, but they did not have a low rate of correct answers.

From the results obtained in this investigation so far, we have evidenced that the bilingualism factor may be acting favourably in the executive control of participants with ADHD. So that we can better contribute to its relevance, we will continue our research with the other participants and analysis of the variables and their respective statistical values. In the future of the investigation of the bilingualism factor, other issues could arise to be studied together, such as dyslexia and language disorders, with the aim of presenting more evidence and materials in this field of research.

6 Conclusion

The objective of this research was to compare the reading times of isolated words between the tested groups, bilinguals with and without ADHD. With our experiment, we proposed to point out possible benefits of bilingualism in the linguistic processing of individuals with ADHD, under the line of Experimental Psycholinguistics. We tested bilingual subjects, Brazilian Portuguese and English, with and without ADHD and found in our initial sample that participants with ADHD had a better response time in the experimental task. Presenting reading times shorter than the control group and correct answer rate balanced with participants without ADHD. Given the linguistic impairment that people with ADHD present in several studies, due to lack of attention, agitation, difficulty finishing a task, etc., the findings found in this research seem so far to diverge from our initial hypothesis, that bilingual participants with ADHD would present equivalent performance compared to bilinguals without ADHD, as in fact they had a better performance and conclude that there are no reading processing problems in the current sample of participants with ADHD. And we add evidence that the bilingualism factor may be acting in a compensatory way in the executive control of participants with ADHD.

We find limitations to our work regarding the model Multilink. The model is capable of explaining the issues of proficiency and lexical access, however we do not have a reference to explain some answers regarding the ADHD and this is a problem that we can continue to work on, as well as the investigation on bilingualism and language impairments.

7 References

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